

Users Perceptions of Resources in an Academic Libraries a Case of University of Education, Winneba

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Abstract:- Over the years, the academic library has witnessed a great transformation in its collections and services due to the preparedness towards the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR). User's satisfaction with library resources is very cardinal as it plays a pivotal role in determining the growth of the library. The study examined users' perception towards the resources of the academic library amidst COVID-19 at the University of Education, Winneba. The study was based on a survey where a questionnaire was employed to solicit data from 294 sample size. The study found that respondents were not aware of some of the library resources especially the electronic types. The study further found a negative perception and satisfaction towards the provision and available library resources and this sends a signal to library management to be proactive in improving upon its services. These negative perception can be attributed to the challenges that the study unravelled as follows; poor user interface designs of some electronic resources, poor signage, poor communication between users and library about any development in the library, experience error whiles using the computers at the library, lack of frequent training for users in new library services. Given this, it was recommended that the library management should focus on orientation and awareness creation, training of users, and provision of library Infrastructure which should encapsulate both manual and electronic infrastructure.

Keywords:- COVID 19. Users' Perception, Collections and Services.

I. INTRODUCTION

The University library has been described by ALA (2010) as the "heart of the University". It is the brain and the center point of intellectual activities. Yusuf and Iwu, (2010) refer to it as the nerve center for scholarship. The purpose of establishing academic libraries is to support the tripartite objectives of teaching, learning, and research, which are fundamental to academia. Apart from this main function, the library is also expected to provide resources for recreation, entertainment and general knowledge for the people within the host community" (Aina, 2004). Library resources are undoubtedly one of the key components in every higher education. For effective teaching, learning and research in an academic environment, Library services cannot be overlooked. The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA, 2003) recognizes this fact and asserts that university libraries are obligatory to the

functioning of universities and the achievement of their academic missions.

Library resources are basically sources of information. Traditionally, these resources were mostly textbooks, magazines, journals, newspapers and other editorials, and encyclopedia, dictionaries, manuals and handbooks, computers, for general use, etc. The resources include both physical and electronic materials. With the advent of the internet, digital sources of information have become prevalent. These digital sources of information include, but not limited to, online libraries and journals, online encyclopedias like Wikipedia, blogs, video blogs like YouTube, etc. Even movie clippings, especially from history, have played a large role in modern research, and hence are classifiable under 'Library Resources'. Library resources also include library personnel (Ademodi, 2004). Libraries of all types need resources ranging from physical library buildings, internet and computer facilities, scanners, photocopier machines, furniture and fittings, proper ventilation in the library, assistive technology, braille, audio-visual tools, multi-purpose vehicles among others. For the library to meet the information needs of users, these resources cannot be swept under the carpet (Ademodi, 2015).

Resources wise, academic libraries in Ghana have failed woefully, many library resources in Ghana are inadequate even though they may not be the only contributing factor as human resource is also a key influencer. Those available are also not well maintained to meet the swelling and complex needs of the user (Alemna, 2001). Despite the important role that academic libraries play in Ghana, they are faced with numerous challenges ranging from swelling student population growth, insufficient library facilities, inadequate resources and insufficient funding, lack of management skills and political willpower to implement policies of which University of Education Winneba Library is no exception.

➤ *Statement of the Problem:*

Every university library today, is trying to demonstrate its value or contribution towards the educational mission of its parent body by impacting on students' education through the provision of improved resources, personnel, and services. Payne and Conyers (2005) investigated the accountability and improvement seeking balance in the value of academic libraries initiatives and it was found that the management of the library had a positive perception about the available resources about the library. Farkas, (2013) also posits that academic libraries should be able to

demonstrate the value of what they are doing and provide evidence of the impact they make which should lead to service improvement. Similarly, Bawa (2018) investigated the awareness and utilization of library resources by students of Tamale Technical University, Ghana. It was brought to the fore that the use of the library resources and facilities was not encouraging and some of the issues were poor internet connectivity, insufficient ICT facilities in the e-library facility.

Anecdotal evidence made by the first researcher in the University of Education Winneba libraries on the main campus, suggests that users had a negative perception towards the availability of library resources due to some perceived challenges. Copious studies have been done on either students', faculty's' perception of the available library resources but few studies have been done on perceptions of both teaching staff and students about available library resources. It is against this background that the researchers find it imperative to conduct this piece of research to fill the knowledge gap that has been identified.

➤ *Purpose of the Study:*

The core purpose of this study is to examine the perception of users of the UEW Library towards the available resources of the University Library. The following are the specific objectives of the study:

- To determine users' awareness and perception of the available resources in the library.
- To determine users' perceptions of the benefits of the available library resources.
- To find out users' satisfaction with available library resources.
- To find out challenges in the use of the available library resources.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *User Awareness and Perception of Available Library Resources in Academic Libraries:*

According to Alis (2005) as cited in Acheampong (2016) highlighted the use of resources and Information Services (EIS) among the users of the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) library in Delhi, India. Data was collected from three hundred library users. The finding revealed that 95 percent of users had awareness about library resources Information Services provided by the library. Internet facilities emerged as the most aware resources and as well as Internet facilities OPAC, CD-ROM. However, online journals fall under average.

In the same vein, Dadzie (2005) investigated the use of electronic resources by students and faculty of Ashesi University, Ghana. The findings revealed that 85 percent of respondents who used the Internet were aware of electronic resources. Most of the users were aware of internet facilities, computers and Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC). Hence the findings show a high awareness of the available resources.

Despite these positive signs, other studies such as Jekere, Omekwu, and Nwoha (2016) report low awareness of the facilities, resources, and services of the digital library at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The study reported lower levels of awareness with the availability of online indexes and abstracts at a mean weight of 1.65 closely followed by other resources such as Video CDs (1.74), VSAT based Internet connectivity (1.90), online Library catalog (1.92), online databases (2.12), etc. The implication of this result is that users are more familiar with using the web and search engines and are less aware of the availability of other useful resources such as portals, online indexes and abstracts and online databases which ought to prove more useful and reliable for research than the search engines.

With respect to students' perception of the value of library resources, the literature reports mixed results. Datig (2014) conducted a study with the goal of developing a student-based perception of libraries that can be used to improve library services and outreach. The study found that students perceive the library resources as a place to develop their greater knowledge. Moreover, students see the library as a bridge between students and the rest of the intellectual world. In summary, the majority of students hold the perception that the library plays an important role in their studies as well as in other areas outside their academic performance. Hence, a positive perception was obtained. However, very few studies in this regard have been conducted in Ghana.

Furthermore, in support of the work of Datig (2014), Dadzie (2005) focused on electronic resources access and usage at Ashesi University College, Ghana. The study found a positive perception of the available electronic resources. It was indicated "electronic resources are invaluable research tools which complement print-based resources in any traditional library.

Nzivo, and Chuanfu (2013) conducted a study with the aim of discovering the met and unmet needs as well as barriers encountered in library use by international students. A survey questionnaire was used to collect data and simple random sampling was employed. The findings of the study revealed that Chinese resources are considerably well perceived by international students. Obasuyi and Idiodi (2015) undertook a study with the objective of determining the value of the university library and its influence on the educational pursuit of students. The study found that students at a Federal University in Nigeria had a positive perception of the available library resources highlighting the library's value to their education and its impact on their academic pursuits and studies, academic performances, productivity, and careers.

But, on the contrary, a few studies have found that some students' retain a negative perception of their Library, Ashaver and Bem-Bura (2013) undertook a study that focused on how users perceive the library resources offered at Benue State University and the Federal University of Agriculture Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. The study found that library users at Benue State University and the Federal

University of Agriculture Makurdi in Nigeria have a negative perception of the resources rendered by these university libraries. The negative perception arises from a lack of awareness by the students on how to search for information materials and ignorance on information search and retrieval strategies. Similar findings were found in the works of (Nzivo and Chuanfu, 2013; Larson and Owusu-Acheaw 2012).

➤ *User Satisfaction with Available Library Resources:*

Satisfaction, as defined by Mostagel (2006), is the art of achieving what one wants. That is satisfying the exact needs of the user. There is no doubt whatsoever that providing the needed services for customers will let them stick to the services of the library.

It is in line with this that Simmonds and Andaleen (1998) evolved the factors of user satisfaction. These factors include competences on the part of library staff in discharging services to users, assurance from all stakeholders, responsiveness, tangible and intangible resources and facilities. On the basis of this model, numerous studies were designed to test the factors for library user satisfaction. Mampu (2009) stated that new and quality service may be said to be satisfactory if they are able to fulfill the needs of and satisfy its customers. Parasuraman et al. (1994) developed the service quality model (SERVQUAL) based on the transactional prescription which makes a comparison between the expected and outcome perceptions of customers with regards to a specific service. It also concluded with suggestions that the library needs to improve on those issues related to the library services and facilities. It has again emphasized the importance of good library services and facilities to support user's satisfaction as there is a significant relationship between the magnitude of the value of the library facilities, resources and service, and library user's satisfaction.

Jekere, Omekwu and Nwoha (2016) undertook a study on the users' perception of the facilities, resources, and services of the Men Digital Library at the University of Nigeria. From the data collected and analyzed, it was found that users' were generally very satisfied with the functional conditions of some of the facilities available at the library particularly with the tables and chairs, the general library environment, air-conditioning, lighting, and ventilation. However, respondents expressed great dissatisfaction with the functionality of some of the facilities such as the desks and storage lockers, bulletin boards, toilet facilities, instructional facilities, etc. This is in line with the findings of Iwhiwhu & Okorodudu (2012) who discovered in their research that users were satisfied with the library space, fans, and air conditions, lightings and ventilation. However, their findings found that users expressed greater dissatisfaction with the photocopier facility and computers.

Further, Larson and Owusu-Acheaw (2012) conducted a study to find out users' satisfaction with services and resources at the Institute for Educational Development and Extension (IEDE) Library at the University of Education, Winneba, Ghana. A descriptive survey design was adopted

for the study and a questionnaire was used for data collection. An availability sampling technique was adopted for the study. The findings reveal that students are satisfied with the availability of internet facilities and materials in the library. In addition, students are satisfied with the efficiency and helpfulness of the staff. Even so, the students perceived the library collection as being outdated.

On the contrary, Gunasekera (200) investigated Students Usage of an Academic Library: a user survey conducted at the Main Library University of Peradeniya, the study was based on descriptive research and the survey research method was used. The findings of the study revealed that most students are dissatisfied with the library's overall performance in meeting their needs. The majority of the respondents were not satisfied with the resources subscriptions to journals related to their field of interest and they preferred to use textbooks and the internet as their major sources of information. Most of them preferred a print format to a digital format. However, it is encouraging to note that a majority of the respondents were satisfied with the service attitude of the library staff.

To satisfy the ever-changing needs of users of the academic library, it is very paramount that, academic libraries be equipped with the necessary resources in order to meet the needs of its users. Adeniran (2011) argues that, if the academic library is not provided with the necessary resources in order to perform its mandate then indeed there is no need for the existence of the academic library since it will become redundant. Ijiekhuamhen, Aghojare, and Ferdinand (2015) uphold that, there must be a frequent appraisal of library services, resources, and to determine the level of user satisfaction, and how the services and resources could be improved to meet the needs of the users.

➤ *Challenges in the Use of Available Library Resources:*

Notwithstanding the efforts of library leaders to meet the needs of their users, other existential factors constantly affect this drive and these range from poor power supply, inadequate ICT equipment and software, skills deficit, among others. Poor power supply, for instance, is an interference on the library's workflow, provision of adequate information services, access to electronic information and the Internet and other online services (Omeluzor, Madukoma, Bamidele & Ogbuiyi, 2012). In this same disposition, Fabunmi and Asubiojo (2013) submitted that the uneven power supply is a problem to accessing OPAC by the students, staff, and librarians of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. In addition, Okiy's research in (2010), found out that, the general low supply of electricity in most parts of Nigeria which in Ghana it is christened "dumsor dumsor" is a key impediment to globalization efforts in academic libraries in Nigeria. This issue is not only peculiar to Nigeria alone but in most African countries of which Ghana is not an exception.

In addition, lack of Information Communication tools, poor internet connectivity among other things were the reasons militating against the use of libraries. These issues are not only peculiar to public libraries but also affect

academic libraries as well. A study conducted by Suleman and Katsektor (2000), found that most users in the Balme Library, University of Ghana were satisfied with the services of the library staff. What this study failed to do was to go a step ahead to find out if they were also satisfied with the resources of the library as well. Oduwale and Akpati (2003) also indicated a lack of ICT and power outages as constraints to the use of electronic resources. In the same vein, Watts and Ibegbulam (2006) discovered the inadequate ICT resources and affordable online access as well as the absence of in-depth ICT skills as key problems. Similarly, Bhatt and Rana (2011) also identified that the most common problems with e-resources are low-speed internet connectivity, lack of awareness about statutory provision for accessing e-resources by the institutions, technical problems, unavailability of sufficient e-resources, doubts in permanency, high purchase price and lack of legal provision. A similar study by Shukla and Mishra (2011) revealed that the majority of research scholars have a problem with low internet connectivity.

Another, Agyen-Gyasi, Lamptey and Frempong (2010) undertook a study on the “Academic Librarians’ Role in Maximizing Library Use in Ghana” and the cardinal problems identified as limiting this role were limited resources and skills necessary to access information in the digital environment. Also, lack of adequate resources was also a bigger challenge such as lack of strong internet connectivity, inadequate ICT facilities, and other facilities

such as small reading rooms, poor washroom. Sambo and Ejiro (2018) undertook a study on the challenges of utilizing library resources by students in the College of Education, Agbor. The study found a numbers of challenges which includes lack of internet facility, unreliable photocopying services within the library 92%, inadequate relevant materials 74%, inadequate functional ICT facilities/lack of user education, unfavourable state of the library 68%, lack of awareness of the library resources 63%, poor reading environment 52% among. This is in line with the findings of Fokomogbon et al (2013), affirmed that “lack of standards in the provision of library services is reported as a major cause of students’ failure of accessing and using relevant informational resources; reducing reading morale, and limiting students’ innovations”. Likewise, Mozeh and Ubwa (2017), in their study, the challenges identified were lack of orientation, the poor state of the library, poor reading environment, and inadequate function of ICT among others.

III. METHODS

The study employs a survey design. Using proportionate sampling method, the study sampled lecturers and students of the University of Education Winneba. With a sample size of 5% which is based on Neuman's (2006) proposition that 5% is adequate for a number above 1000, the sample size for this study was 294 out of a population of 5888. Population and proportionate sample size of library users are presented as follows:

Table 1 Population and Sampling

Library users	Population	Proportionate sample size
Postgraduate students	964	49
4 th -year undergraduates	4476	224
Teaching staff	448	22
Total	5888	294

In respect to data collection instrument, this study used both open-ended and close-ended questionnaire. Data was collected at the library using the convenience approach. The researcher gave questionnaires to users who visited the library at the time of data collection. The intent was that it enabled the researcher to get the right people who visit the library in order to obtain relevant information. The researcher distributed the questionnaire until the expected number was obtained. Users who preferred to send the

questionnaire and return it later were allowed. In addition, the researcher took the contact of those who preferred to answer the questionnaire at their own convenient time. IBM’s Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was used to analyze the data collected from the respondents. Results were presented in the form of tables and charts by using descriptive tools such as frequencies and percentages. The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *User Awareness of the Available Resources:*

Respondents were asked to indicate whether they were aware of the available resources at the University of Education, Winneba Library. The responses are shown in Figure 1:

Fig 1 Users' Awareness of the Available Resources

From Figure 1, 260 (93%) representing the highest portion of the respondents confirmed in affirmative that they are aware of the resources provided by the library while others 20 (7%) responded otherwise. This is a general impression of the awareness of the available resources, however, individual resources may differ to the extent of been known to the potential library users.

➤ *Channel of Awareness of the Available Resources:*

Respondents were asked to indicate the channel through which they found out about the available resources. Table 2 depicts their responses:

Table 2 Channel Of Awareness Of The Available Resources

Channels Of Awareness	Yes		No	
	Freq.	100%	Freq.	100%
Colleagues	150	54	130	46
Notices	56	20	224	80
Library website	69	25	211	75
Orientation	110	39	170	61
Course lecturers	130	46	150	54

As seen from the table from Table 2, the majority of 150 (54%) of the respondents got to know the available library resources through colleagues, followed by course lecturers constituting 130 (46%) of the total respondents. Also, others were through orientation 110 (39%), Library website 69 (25%) and notice 56(20%). It can, therefore, be inferred that the library isn't active in marketing its product through the traditional channels; notices, website, and orientation. Since marketing is critical in the patronage of library services, the findings are a wakeup call for the library to harness its publicity of the available library resources.

➤ *Awareness of the Various Available Resources:*

Awareness is a determinant of the extent of the use of any available resources. It is blatant that, without awareness, potential users will not be in a position even to decide to use or not use the available resources. Based on this overview, respondents were asked to indicate as many as possible how they became aware of the available resources provided by the UEW Library as shown in Table 3:

Table 3 Respondents Awareness of the Available Resources

Available library resources	Yes		No	
	Freq.	100%	Freq.	100%
Printed books on subjects areas	270	96	10	4
E-Books	120	43	180	29
past questions	70	25	110	39
conference proceedings	61	22	219	79
thesaurus	58	21	222	79
dictionaries	90	32	190	68

bibliographies	55	20	225	80
yearbooks	39	14	241	86
almanacs	56	20	224	80
encyclopedias,	50	18	130	82
E-journals	150	54	130	46
daily newspapers	90	32	190	68
Online databases	110	36	170	61
Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)	160	57	120	43
CD-ROMs	110	39	170	61
printers	155	55	125	45
scanners	134	48	146	52
photocopier machines	160	57	120	43

As shown in Table 3, the majority of the respondents 270(96%) were aware of the printed books on subject areas. 160 (57%) of the respondents were aware of the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), likewise, 160 (57%) of them were aware of the photocopier machines, followed by E-Journals 150 (54%). Also, awareness of the yearbooks and other related materials; encyclopedias 50(18%), almanacs 56(20%), thesaurus 58(21%) and bibliographies 55 (20%) were considerably low. These findings depict that, the library has not strengthened its marketing of resources very well and it calls for more room for improvement.

➤ *Perception of the Available Resources in the Library:*

The respondents were requested to indicate their perception of the various resources in the library. Table 4 summarizes their perception:

Table 4 Perception of the Available Resources

Available Resources	Responses					
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Non-responses
The library has enough and current books to cover my information needs	45 (16%)	70(25%)	65 (23%)	55 (20%)	39 (14%)	6 (2%)
There are enough and well scholarly journals to meet my information needs	39 (14%)	90 (32%)	70 (25%)	50 (18%)	31 (11%)	-
The library provides daily newspapers and other academic magazines	49 (18%)	69 (25%)	65 (23%)	70 (25%)	25 (9%)	2 (1%)
There are enough computers and CD-ROM for users	59 (21%)	98 (35%)	45 (16%)	59 (21%)	17 (6%)	-
The library has strong and reliable internet facility to facilitate teaching, research and learning.	60 (21%)	110 (39%)	60 (21%)	30 (11%)	20 (7%)	-
There are enough printers scanners and photocopier machines to help users	55 (20%)	80 (29%)	90 (32%)	29 (10%)	26 (9%)	-
The library portals hold wide coverage of digital/electronic resources of the university library, available 24 hours a day.	39 (14%)	75 (27%)	110(39%)	39 (14%)	17 (6%)	-
The library has current e-books and printed books for users	40 (14%)	80 (29%)	90 (32%)	50 (18%)	18 (6%)	2 (1%)
The library has adequate physical space for research and studies	44 (16%)	63 (23%)	44 (16%)	90 (32%)	30 (11%)	9(3%)
The library has adequate and suitable chairs for studies	24 (9%)	54 (19%)	50(18%)	110 (39%)	40(14%)	2 (1%)
The library has adequate suitable tables for studies	26 (9%)	60 (21%)	34(12%)	130 (46%)	20 (7%)	10(4%)
There are enough reading rooms specifically allocated for users	34 (12%)	44 (16%)	80 (29%)	90 (32%)	32 (11%)	-
The library has adequate discussion rooms for users	70 (25%)	95 (34%)	50 (18%)	35(13%)	25 (9%)	5(2%)
There are enough database subscriptions	55 (20%)	34 (12%)	120(43%)	30 (11%)	23 (8%)	18 (6%)
The library has adequate security measures to ensure its users and resources are safe	30 (11%)	32(11%)	150(54%)	45 (16%)	20(7%)	3 (1%)
The library has a good lighting system to aid learning	16 (6%)	49(18%)	55(20%)	90 (32%)	65 (23%)	5 (5%)

The library has good air-conditioning that aid ventilation	56 (20%)	86 (31%)	80 (31%)	39 (14%)	17 (6%)	2 (1%)
The library has a large parking space for users and staff with vehicles	60 (21%)	120(43%)	44(16%)	20(7%)	36(13%)	-
There are adequate and neat washroom for users	50 (18%)	75(27%)	55(20%)	70(25%)	30(11%)	-
The library has good signage to show directions	39(14%)	69(25%)	77(28%)	65(23%)	30(11%)	-
The library has enough multi-sockets to connect personal laptops	70 (25%)	140(50%)	50(18%)	15(5%)	5(2%)	-

As shown in Table 4, out of 280 respondents 70(25%) disagree with the statement “The library has enough and current books to cover my information needs” 65 (23%) indicated neutral 55 (20%) agree. It is noticeable that the perception of the respondents was skewed towards negative perception and it gives a clear suggestion that the library collection is not current enough to meet the information needs of the library users.

Also on the statement “The library provides daily newspapers and other academic magazines” the majority of the respondents 70 (25%) indicated agree, 69 (25%) disagree, 65 (23%) were neutral. Therefore, these findings bring to bear that, users have a negative perception towards the available daily newspapers and other academic magazines even though the difference between positive and negative perception was significant. With the statement “There is enough computers and CD-ROM for users” majority of the respondents 98 (35%) disagree, 59 (21%) strongly agree and the same number disagree while 45 (16%) were neutral signifying negative perception towards the computers and CD-ROM available at the library. On the assertion “The library has strong and reliable internet facility to facilitate teaching, research, and learning.” The majority of the respondents 110 (39%) disagree, 60 (21%) strongly disagree and the same number were ambivalent while 30 (11%) agree. It can, therefore, be seen that the available internet facilities which will aid users to access library resources especially the electronics are not in good standing as far as the perceptions of the respondents are concern.

Further, 90 (32%) of the respondents representing the majority were neutral to the statement “There are enough printers, scanners and photocopier machines to help users” 80 (29%) disagree while 29 (10%) agree. It can be inferred that the library needs to add more printers, scanners and photocopier machines to enable users utilize the available resources.

Also, a greater number 110 (39%) of them did not take any stand on the fact that the library portals hold wide coverage of digital/electronic resources of the university library available 24 hours in a day, 75 (27%) disagree, 39 (14%) strongly disagree and the same number 39 (14%)

agree. These findings are indications that the coverage of the available digital resources is not enough since users have varies of information need. Lastly, the majority of the respondents were not sure whether the library has current e-books and printed books for users, 80 (29%) disagree and 50 (18%) agree.

Addition, 95 (34%) representing the majority of the respondents reacted to the assertion that “the library has adequate discussion rooms for users” by indicating disagree, 70 (25%) strongly disagree, 50 (18%) were undecided and 25 (9%) agreed. Holistically, these findings suggest that the library needs more discussion rooms as a greater portion of respondents strongly disagree that the library has adequate discussion rooms. More room is need in the library to accommodate users who will like to have discussions.

Further, on the statement “there are enough database subscriptions”, 120 (43%) of the respondents neither agree nor disagree, 55 (20%) strongly agree and while 23 (8%) strongly disagree. This indicates that respondents had not explored the available subscribed databases provided by the library. Therefore, the library needs to create massive awareness of the available resources especially the subscribed database.

On the perception of the place of convenient, 75(27%) disagree with the statement that there is adequate and neat washroom for users, 50 (18%) strongly agree, 70(25%) agree and 30(11%) strongly disagree. These findings suggest that respondents do not really have a good perception of the place of convenient provided and need to be improved.

Again, 77(28%) were on undecided whether the library has good signage to show directions, 69(25%) disagree and least number 30(11%) of the respondents strongly agree and on the statement “the library has enough multi-sockets to connect personal laptops” majority of the respondent 140(50%) agree, 70 (25%) Strongly disagree, and small number 15(5%) number agree. This reaction from the respondents suggests that the library is doing well in terms of providing enough multi-sockets for them to charge their laptops and other gadgets such as PC-tablet, cellular phones to mention but a few which aid in learning and research.

Table 5 Overall Impression of the Perception of the Available Resources

Negative Impression		Percent	Moderate Extent	Positive Impression		Percent
Strongly disagree	960	38%	1484	Strongly Agree	566	25%
Disagree	1593	62%		Agree	1211	47%
2553		100	595	1777		100

From Table 5, the overall impression shows that users have a negative perception towards the available resources as 1593 (62%) disagreed, and 960 (38%) strongly disagreed and Agree 1211 (47%) and 566 (25%) signifying positive impression. These findings are indication that users of the library are not pleased with the available library resources as the majority of respondents’ perception was negative. These findings are consistent with the works of (Obasuyi and Idiodi, 2015; Larson and Owusu-Acheaw, 2012) where it was revealed that respondents had a negative perception towards the available resources provided by the library, also consistent with the works of (Malatji, 2017; Nyantakyi-Baah, 2016).

However, it supported the works of Ashaver and Bem-Bura, 2013; Datig, 2014; Dadzie, 2005; Nzivo and Chuanfu, 201 who found positive perception towards the available library resources.

➤ *Perceptions on the Benefit of the Available Library Resources:*

Respondents were also asked to indicate what the available library resources have had on their learning abilities.

Table 6 Perceptions on the Benefit of the Available Library Resources

Items	Responses					
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	No response
Access to library materials aid my research work and learning	50 (18%)	70 (23%)	48 (17%)	63 (23%)	40 (14%)	9(3%)
The available library resource helps me to meet my information needs.	55 (20%)	70 (25%)	68(24%)	52 (19%)	32(11%)	3(1%)
There are well-resourced library materials that motivate me to carry out my academic work without many hurdles.	60 (21%)	55 (20%)	68(24%)	60 (46%)	34 (12%)	3(1%)
I am able to access online library resources in the comfort of my home.	60 (21%)	63 (23%)	38 (14%)	85 (30%)	32 (11%)	2(1%)
Using library materials cut down my expense on lecture materials and journal articles that requires subscriptions.	30 (11%)	40 (14%)	100 (36%)	69(25%)	37 (9%)	4(1%)
It helps me to expand my knowledge-base and excel in my academics.	29 (10%)	42 (15%)	90(32%)	69 (25%)	35(13%)	3 (6%)
There are always Help Desk who assist me in retrieving information without any stress.	30 (11%)	32(11%)	150 (54%)	45 (16%)	20(7%)	3(1%)
The library provides compiled past questions for students which help examination.	68 (24%)	80(29%)	40(14%)	54(19%)	30(19%)	8(3%)
The library collection contains current materials to support the research study.	65(23%)	40(14%)	78 (28%)	59(21%)	35 (13%)	3 (1%)

As seen from Table 6, it is evident that majority of the respondents 70 (23%) disagreed to the fact that the library materials aid them in their research work and learning, 63 (23%) agreed, 50 (18%) strongly disagreed while 48 (17%) undecided and strongly agreed 40 (14%).

Also the statement “The available library resource help me to meet my information needs” greater portion of the respondent 70 (25%) disagreed, 68(24%) did not take any stand, 55 (20%) strongly disagreed, 52 (19%) agreed while 32(11%) disagreed. Addition, it was reported in the

table that, a considerable number of the respondents 68(24%) representing the majority were ambivalent to the fact that there are well-resourced library materials that motivate them to carry out their academic work without many hurdles, 60 (21%) strongly agreed, 55 (20%) agreed. And on the other hand, 60 (46%) agreed while 34 (12%) strongly agreed.

Further, on the statement “I am able to access online library resources at the comfort of my home” 85 (30%) of the total respondents disagreed, 63 (23%) agreed, 60 (21%) strongly disagreed, 38 (14%) were neutral and 32 (11%)

strongly agreed. Addition, the statement, “I am able to access online library resources at the comfort of my home.” 85 (30%) of the respondents agreed, 63 (23%) disagreed and 60 (21%) strongly disagreed, 38 (14%) and 32 (11%) were neutral and strongly agreed respectively. Again, on the assertion “Using library materials cut down my expense on lecture materials and journal articles that require subscriptions” majority of the respondents 100 (36%) were not decided, 40 (14%) disagreed and 30 (11%) strongly disagreed. Also, on the same assertion, 69(25%) agreed whiles 37 (9%) strongly agreed. Further, 90(32%) of the respondents representing the majority of the agreed on the fact that the available library resources help them to expand their knowledge-base and excel in their academics, 69 (25%) agreed, 42 (15%) disagreed and 29 (10%) strongly disagree whiles 35(13%) strongly agreed. Again, on the statement “There are always Help Desk who assist me in retrieving information without any stress”, majority of the respondents 150 (54%) were neutral, 45 (16%) agreed and 20(7%) strongly disagreed. On the other hand, 32 (11%) of

the respondents disagreed while 30 (11%) strongly disagreed.

Additionally, 80(29%) out of the total respondents disagreed with the fact that the library provides compiled past questions for students which help examination, 68 (24%) strongly disagreed whiles 54(19%) and 30 (19%) agreed and strongly agreed. Also, 78 (28%) of the respondents representing the majority were neutral to the fact that library collection contains current materials to support research studies, 65(23%) strongly disagree and 40(14%) disagreed. Also, 59(21%) 35 (13%) “agreed” and “strongly agreed” with the construct respectively.

➤ *Overall all Impressions on the User Perceptions on the Benefit of the Available Library Resources:*

Table 7 User Perceptions on the Benefit of the Available Library Resources

Negative Impression		Percent (%)	Moderate Extent	Positive Impression		Percent
Strongly Disagree	447	49	680	Agree	556	65
Disagree	460	51		Strongly Agree	295	35
	907	100			851	100

As shown in the table above, it can be seen that the general impression of the perception of the available library resources is negative (907). Thus the majority of the responses which encapsulate 447 (49%) and 460 (51%) were skewed towards negative impression followed 556 (65%) and 295 (35%) of the respondents representing the 907 responses showed positive impression, whiles 680 responses indicate moderate extent. This finding is a wakeup call to the Management of the University of Education Winneba library to improve upon its library resources. These findings are inconsistent with the study by Dickenson (2006) who undertook a study on academic library impact study (ALIS), of academic library usage and outcomes, involving nine colleges and university users` perceived the available library materials as useful which ultimately aid them in fulfilling their academic goals and objectives. Also, the findings did not support the works of Montgomery and King (2002) who found out in their research that library collections especially electronic format result in some overall reductions in library costs, especially when total processing and space costs are taken into account. The study found the positive usefulness of the available library resources. Similar contrary findings also found in the works of Johari and Zainab (2007) who reported that facilities provided in a library are very useful

to the users. In effect, the majority of the users were found utilizing the library resources because they perceived the available resources as easy access to information, quality library materials, etc.

On the other hand, the findings are congruent with the works Malatji (2017) who investigated students’ perceptions of the role of the library in their studies at Tshwane University of technology, Polokwane campus. The findings showed a negative perception of the available library resources. It also supports the study by Nyantakyi-Baah (2016) which focuses on the user perception of academic library service quality and value of the Ghana Institute of Journalism and Ashesi University College Libraries. It was revealed that users of the library had a negative perception of the available library resources.

➤ *User Satisfaction with the Available Library Resources:*

It is blatant that user satisfaction of library resources plays a key role in the extent of its use. If users are satisfied, they will be willing to use the available library resources. In view of this background, respondents were asked to indicate the extent of their satisfaction towards the available resources as shown in Table 8:

Table 8 Respondents Level of Satisfaction of the Available Library Resources

Items	Not at all	To a small extent	moderate extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent	No. Responses
The library makes it is easy for me to find information that I need for my research and learning	30 (11%)	55 (20%)	80 (29%)	60 (21%)	55 (20%)	-
I am very comfortable with the space in the library	45 (16%)	90 (32%)	58 (21%)	49 (18%)	38 (14%)	-
I always find a place to sit when I use the library.	30 (11%)	48 (17%)	60 (21%)	98 (35%)	42 (15%)	2 (1%)
The constant supply of power helps me to study anytime in the library	80 (29%)	63 (23%)	69 (25%)	55 (20%)	13 (5%)	-
The library is able to meet all my information needs	56 (20%)	50 (18%)	120(43%)	26(9%)	28(100%)	-
The library offers me the opportunity to access numerous scholarly journals	44 (16%)	66 (24%)	61 (22%)	49 (18%)	60(21%)	-
I am very satisfied with the internet facilities in the library	78 (28%)	60 (21%)	75 (27%)	44 (16%)	21 (8%)	2(1%)
I am very satisfied with the computer facilities in the library.	50 (18%)	81 (29%)	69 (25%)	36 (13%)	44 (16%)	3 (1%)

From Table 8, it can be observed that a sizeable number of the respondents moderately reacted to the assertion “the library makes it is easy for me to find information that I need for my research and learning”, 60 (21%) agreed to a large extent, 50(20%) indicated “To a small extent” and another 50(20%) indicated “To a very large extent” and 30 (11%) indicated “Not at all.” In as much as the level of satisfaction was rated high as moderate still suggests that the library does not really present its services in a way that users like.

Also, majority 90 (32%) of the respondents agreed to a small extent that they are very comfortable with the space in the library, 58 (21%) indicated moderate and a small number 49 (18%) indicated “To a large extent”. This suggests that the library is not spacious to the users. On the assertion, “I always find a place to sit when I use the library” greater number 98 (35%) agreed to a large extent, 48 (17%) indicated to a small extent and 60 (21%) of the respondents reacted with moderate satisfaction.

Further, majority 80 (29%) of the respondents expressed their dissatisfaction towards the statement “The constant supply of power helps me to study anytime in the library” by indicating “not at all”, 69 (25%) of the respondents level of satisfaction was moderate while 13 (5%) of them indicated “to a large extent”. The finding is an indication that the library needs to relook at the power supply in the library to ensure constant accessibility of the library and its resources.

Further, almost half 120(43%) representing the majority of the respondents reacted to the stated “The library is able to meet all my information needs” by indicating “moderate extent”, 50 (18%) indicated to a small extent whilst 26(9%) indicated to “large extent while”. This means that respondents are facing some challenges in the

quest to look for information to meet their information needs. Also, to the statement “the library offers me the opportunity to access numerous scholarly journals” 66 (24%) indicated their level of satisfaction with “to a small extent”, 61 (22%) indicated a moderate extent, 44 (16%) selected not at all. This means, that, there might be some setbacks blocking their chance from accessing the numerous scholarly journals provided by the library and no wonder the majority of the respondents were dissatisfied by indicating to a small extent.

Again, it can be seen from the table that, greater percentage of the respondents 78 (28%) indicate “not at all” to the assertion “I am very satisfied with the internet facilities in the library”, 75 (27%) were moderately satisfied, while 21 (8%) of them expressed their satisfaction by indicating concern. It can be inferred that respondents were not satisfied with the internet facilities provided by the library.

Further, 81 (29%) expressed their satisfaction to the assertion “I am very satisfied with the computer facilities in the library” by indicating “to a small extent”, the satisfaction 69 (25%) of the respondents were moderate, 36 (13%) indicated “to a large extent”. The findings suggest that respondents are not satisfied with the computer facilities available in the library.

Again, it can be seen from Table 5 that, considerable number of the respondents 70 (25%) of them expressed their satisfaction by indicating to a large extent to the statement “I am able to access the online databases anytime anywhere”, 59 (21%) chose not at all while 45 (16%) indicated “To a very large extent”. It can be inferred from the findings that, respondents can get access to the subscribed database base irrespective of their geographical location.

Table 9 Overall Impression of the Level of Satisfaction of the Available Library Resources

NEGATIVE IMPRESSION		PERCENT	MODERATE EXTENT	POSITIVE IMPRESSION		PERCENT
Not at all	472	47%	640	To a large extent	528	60%
To a small extent	530	53%		To a very large extent	346	40%
1002		100	640	874		100

As indicated in Table 9, the overall impression of the level of satisfaction of the available resources is not satisfactory where the majority of the responses were skewed towards negative, Thus the total responses showing negative satisfaction were as follows Not at all 472 (47%) and To a small extent 530 (53%). However, a number of them showed a positive impression in terms of satisfaction as follows; 528 (60%) to a large extent and to a very large extent 346 (40%). Comparing the overall impression, it can, therefore, be seen that, users’ of the library had negative satisfaction towards the available resources. These findings support the works of (Gunasekera, 2000; Adeniran, 2011, Ferdinand, 2015) where negative satisfaction was revealed and incongruent with the studies by (Larson and Owusu-

Acheaw, 201; Bhatti, 2013 Khan, Bhatti, Khan, and Ismail, 2014; Malatji, 2017; Khan, Bhatti, Khan and Ismail, 2014) in which positive impression towards the level of satisfaction of the available resources were revealed.

➤ *Challenges in the Use of the Available Library Resources:*

There is no deniable fact that a library can be in existence without challenges mitigating against its progress. In view of this respondents were asked to indicate as many as possible, the challenges they think are affecting the library resources as well as the provision of resources. Responses from respondents are shown in Table 10.

Table 10 Challenges in the use of the Available and Library Resources

Items.	YES		NO	
	Freq.	100%	Freq.	100
Poor internet access speed	160	57	120	43
Inadequate computers	149	53	131	47
Poor lighting systems	79	28	101	36
Poor washroom.	90	32	190	68
The library is not spacious enough to accommodate users	115	41	165	59
Poor user interface designs of some electronic resources	100	36	180	64
Poor signage	169	60	111	40
Poor communication between users and library staff about any development in the library	181	65	99	35
Library staff are not knowledgeable in information retrieval system.	98	35	182	65
Experience error whiles using the computers at the library	136	49	144	51
lack of frequent training for users in new library services	189	68	91	33
lack of awareness of most of the library resources	199	71	81	33

From Table 10, one of the critical challenges mitigating the progress of the library was “lack of awareness of most of the library resources” as the majority of the respondents 199 (71%) confirmed in affirmative. Also, 189 (68%) of the respondents indicated a lack of frequent training for users in new library services and in terms of communication 181 (65%) of the respondents selected “Poor communication between users and library about any development in the library” as a challenge. Other challenges were as follows; Poor internet access speed emerges as a challenge in which a considerable number of responses 160 (57%) skewed to negative, Inadequate computers 149 (53%), The library is not spacious enough to accommodate users 115 (41%), Poor user interface designs of some electronic resources 100 (36%), Library staffs are not knowledgeable in an information retrieval system 98 (35%), Poor washroom 90 (32%), Poor lighting systems 79 (28%).

The findings from the challenges indicate that awareness of the available library especially resources are not in good standing. It is obvious that, when users are not aware of the available resources, they will not be in a better position even to decide to use or not to use. This is a wakeup

call for the library since the marketing of library resources is now a compelling activity with the ultimate goal to win back lost library users and to maintain the interest of the current user. These findings collaborate with the works of (Ejiro, 2018; Ubwa, 2017)

It can also be seen that training of library users is another critical challenge especially, with the electronic resources, its utilization mainly depends on the level of skills that potential users possess. There can be an abundance of electronic resources coupled with massive publicity of library resource but if users do not have the skills to use or retrieve electronic information, underutilization will still be observed. The findings are consistent with the works of Agyen-Gyasi, Lamptey, and Frempong, 2010; Adika (2003) where inadequate training was a big issue in the use of available library resources. Again, poor communication when observed can hamper the progress of the provision of library services.

Also, a considerable number of the respondents indicated, internet facility as a challenge in the library. It is obvious that, the explosion of the internet has geared the

focus of most libraries in the provision of digital library service, therefore, internet facilities are compelling as far as the use of electronic library resources is concerned. Similar findings were found in the works of (Katsepor, 2000, Bhatt & Rana2011; Shukla & Mishra, 2011).

V. CONCLUSION

It is evident that the main goal of the university library is for users to gain access to its abundant wealth of information resources. Information sources are efficient if they provide relevant, useful and accurate information that can help users solve their problems. Accessibility of library resources means the ease of locating and retrieving a piece of information from the storage medium. The library which is the lifeblood of every institution performs phenomenal roles in teaching and learning with its resources. As indicated in this study, even though users of the University of Education Winneba were aware of the library resources, they had unpleasant perceptions towards the available resources, which includes, its usefulness, satisfaction and expected quality were below the bar. Also, the users were saddled with challenges such as poor internet access speed, inadequate computers, the library is not spacious enough to accommodate users, poor user interface designs of some electronic resources, poor signage, poor communication between users and library about any development in the library, experience error whiles using the computers at the library, lack of frequent training for users in new library services, lack of awareness of most of the library resources. For the library to obtain maximum utilization of its resources which is the main ultimate goal, management of the library, stakeholders and the government should exert conscious effort to put measures in place in order to arrest these challenges to the barest minimum.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study:

➤ Orientation And Awareness Creation

As it is said if users are not aware of the existence of resources they will not be in a position to utilize it. The management of the library should organize orientation especially first-year students and also to the continuous students as well as faculty members about the available library resources. The library should endeavor to utilize all the available channels such as exhibition, the university website, social media, occasions to mention but a few to market the available library materials since, marketing is now a compelling activity if a library wants to win back lost users, maintain current users and attract new users.

➤ Training

User training is vital to ensure that library resources especially the electronic ones are better used in the library since a large number of library patrons are in recent times searching electronic literature on their own. Users of e-resources should be taught advanced search strategies and the use of controlled vocabulary languages to make electronic search processes much easier for them to fully

utilize the available electronic journals and database. Thus, there is a need for UEW's governing body to integrate enough Information Technology Literacy contents into the curriculum for members of the University environment. Non-users of resources should be identified and proper steps should be taken to train and convert them into potential users of resources. This will go a long way to increase students' awareness of resources at the UEW.

➤ Infrastructure

Laptop PCs with wireless connections to the internet should be provided. Internet access allows users to access the internet in virtually any environment away from cable-connected PCs. The Internet and the World Wide Web provides access to enormous amounts of information (mostly through electronic resources), some of which are for free and others are subscribed for a fee. Authorities of the University should consider an upgrade of the wireless connection available at the Library for use by students within any corner of the library. This will help prevent the overcrowding of the Library's e-resources section by users because, with the wireless internet connection, students can sit anywhere within the vicinity of the library or even outside it to access the electronic resources without having to necessarily visit the e-resources section in order to use them. Authorities can also explore the use of an effective "off-campus access" system to electronic resources, where users are registered into a well-designed system which permits them access to the electronic resources away from campus.

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